

THE RELATION BETWEEN SELF-ESTEEM AND JOB SATISFACTION OF PROVINCIAL DIRECTORS OF YOUTH SERVICES AND SPORTS

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Abstract:

While the purpose of this research is to investigate the relation between the job satisfaction and self-esteem of provincial directors of youth and sports, their self-esteem and job satisfaction has also been investigated with regard to some demographic variables. As data collection tools, “Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory”, “Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale” and “Demographic Information Form” developed by Stanley Coopersmith have been used. The statistics of Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U and Correlation Analysis have been used in the research. Following the statistics performed, a significant difference hasn’t been established between the variables of self-esteem of the participants, age, educational background, term of employment, term of employment as a manager, sex and marital status. No significant difference has been found between the job satisfaction of participants and sex; between the term of employment and term of employment as a manager. It has been determined that the scores of the individuals with a bachelor’s degree are significantly higher than those having master’s or PhD degree in the sub-dimensions of extrinsic satisfaction, intrinsic satisfaction and general satisfaction in job satisfaction, there is a significant difference between the extrinsic sub-dimension scores of the participants and the variable of age, extrinsic satisfaction scores of the individuals aged 40 and above are significantly higher than the individuals aged between 30-34. According to the results of Spearman correlation analysis, it has been ascertained that there is a negatively moderate relation between the self-esteem and extrinsic satisfaction and a positively moderate relation is in question between the self-esteem and general satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Organizations have emerged from the need of individuals to cooperate with each other in order to achieve certain goals they aim in social life. In order for organizations to survive, they need a common aim to be realized and the individuals willing to realize this aim and communicating with each other. Sports organizations, which are open systems, aim to provide sports to individuals, to disseminate it in the society and to realize sports services. In order for sports organizations to achieve this purpose, there is a need for highly productive, enthusiastic and self-confident employees having high performance within the organization, contributing to the efficiency of the organization and feeling themselves effective and successful (Akbulut, 2015:2).

One of the most important and necessary conditions for employees to be successful, happy and productive is the concept of "self-esteem" that guides the personality traits of employees. The self is the sum of the individual's physical and mental characteristics, it means the recognition and evaluation of all these characteristics that the individual possesses (Sarıçam, 2013:224). The self is not merely an assessment of the individual's particular characteristics but a reaction to the same environment in the direction of his/her experiences by perceiving his/her surroundings as a result of the relation, communication and interaction with this surrounding (Özerkan, 2004:109).

Self-Esteem is a structure emerging as feeling oneself valuable, being accepted, liked in the society, revealing the skills, knowledge and abilities, succeeding and boasting about the achievements and acceptance and adoption of their own physical characteristics and structured following the self-judgement and self-assessment and it is fed from three main sources such as respect of others, competency and assessment of these two sources by individuals for themselves (selfdom) (Özkan, 1994:4).

Occupational satisfaction - which directs the business life of employees, makes them happy and peaceful in the working environment and carries them to the success in the business life - expresses a pleasant emotional valuation arising from the work or work experiences of employees, i.e. and what they think and how they feel about the work (Colquitt et al. 2015:98). Job satisfaction is a very important structure in organizational behavior and it is related to important results including job performance, organizational citizenship behavior, absenteeism and life satisfaction (Heller et al. 2002:815).

There are varieties of factors that enable job satisfaction to realize at different levels. While the factors such as personality, previous experiences, age, sex, educational background and duration of service are considered as individual factors, job itself and its place in society, opportunities for promotion, recognition, working conditions, managerial attitudes, physical environment, employee relations, whether the job is suitable for the individual and the factors related to rewards are among the organizational factors (Aşık, 2010:37).

Self-Esteem and job satisfaction emerge as an important concept that can be met by the interactions of both organizations and those who work in organizations. Therefore, "self-esteem and job satisfaction" is highly important and directly proportional both to the provincial directors being the employees of the directorate of youth services and sports called as a sports organization and to the degree at which level the sports organization they belong to can reach its targets. This highly important organic connection reveals the necessity of determining the job satisfaction and self-esteem of provincial directors of youth services and sports and evaluating the relation between them in the dilemma of provincial directors of youth services and sports and sports organization (Aydoğan, 2012:2).

2. Research Method

This is a survey model research. The research population is composed of the Provincial Directors of Youth Services and Sports serving during 2014-2015 in 81 provinces. Below-mentioned measurement tools have been used in 49 of these Provincial Directors of Youth Services and Sports.

2.1 Data Collection Tools

"Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory", *"Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale"* and *"Demographic Information Form"* have been applied to the participants in the research.

A. Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory

It is a measurement tool developed by Stanley Coopersmith in 1986 and used in the assessment of the attitudes of individuals in different areas by themselves and its adaptation into Turkish, reliability and validity studies have been conducted by Turan and Tufan (1987) (Turan et al; 1987:816). There are some studies supporting the reliability (r:0.80 and above) and validity of re-test about the scale and Coopersmith (1959) has also revealed 0.88 points (more than 5 weeks) and 0.77 points (more than 3 years) reliability of re-test. For Kuder-Richardson, total score of the scale is 0.91 (for females) and 0.80 (for males) and Cronbach alpha coefficient is 0.86 (Pişkin, 1996:178).

B. Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale (Form III)

Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale was developed by Weiss, Dawis England and Lofquist in 1967 and adapted into Turkish by Oran in 1989. The reliability coefficient of the original scale is .83. The reliability study in Turkey was performed by Yıldırım in 1996 and Cronbach alpha coefficient was found to be .90 and test re-test reliability coefficient was found as .76 (Yıldırım, 2007:264). Minnesota job satisfaction scale is a five-point Likert type scale scored from 1 to 5 and it is composed of 20 items with intrinsic, extrinsic and general satisfaction levels having deterministic characteristics (Yılmaz et al; 2009:205).

C. Demographic Information Form

It consists of questions aimed at gathering information on the sex, age and education of the participant administrators.

2.2 Data Analysis

Kruskal Wallis and Mann Whitney U were used in assessment of research data and the statistics of Correlation Analysis were used in testing the relation between the job satisfaction and self-esteem of the provincial directors of youth services and sports. (SPSS 21.0) package program was used in data analysis. Cronbach alpha coefficients were determined as .87 for self-esteem, .83 for Intrinsic satisfaction, .87 for Extrinsic satisfaction and .91 for General satisfaction.

3. Findings

Table 1: Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between self-esteem of participants and the variables of age, education, term of employment, term of employment as manager

Self-esteem	Demographic Characteristics	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P
Age	20-24	0	0	5.401	.145
	25-29	1	45.00		
	30-34	3	38.50		
	35-40	8	25.63		
	40 and above	37	23.23		
Education	Primary and Secondary School	0	0	3.216	.200
	High School	0	0		
	Associate Degree	1	1.00		
	Bachelor's Degree	36	24.93		
	Master's Degree and PhD	12	27.21		

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Term of Employment	1-5	3	38.50	5.740	.125
	6-10	0	0		
	11-15	4	35.25		
	16-20	13	22.42		
	20 and above	29	23.34		
Term of Employment as Manager	1-5	37	26.46	6.449	.168
	6-10	4	24.75		
	11-15	3	31.33		
	16-20	1	16.00		
	20 and above	4	9.25		

Following the Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between self-esteem of participants and the variables of age, education, term of employment, term of employment as manager, no significant difference has been found between the self-esteem and the relevant variables.

Table 2: Mann Whitney U analysis results regarding the relation between self-esteem of the participants and the variable of sex

Sex	Demographic Characteristics	N	Mean Rank	Z	P
	Female	1	25.50	25.50	-.036
	Male	48	24.99		

Following the Mann Whitney U analyses conducted between the self-esteem of the participants and the variable of sex, no significant difference has been found between the self-esteem and the relevant variables.

Table 3: Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between job satisfaction levels of the participants and the variable of age

	Age	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P
Intrinsic Satisfaction	20-24	0	0	4.149	.246
	25-29	1	25.50		
	30-34	3	10.83		
	35-39	8	30.38		
	40 and above	37	24.97		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	20-24	0	0	8.475	.037*
	25-29	1	3.00		
	30-34	3	6.67		
	35-39	8	29.38		
	40 and above	37	26.14		
General Satisfaction	20-24	0	0	6.899	.075
	25-29	1	4.00		

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	30-34	3	9.00		
	35-39	8	29.50		
	40 and above	37	25.89		

*p<0.05

It has been determined following the analysis results that there is a significant difference between the extrinsic job satisfaction sub-dimension scores of the participants and the variable of age. Mann Whitney U statistics has been performed with the purpose of determining the source of emerging significance.

Accordingly, extrinsic satisfaction scores of the individuals aged 40 and above ($X=21.73$) are significantly higher than the individuals aged between 30 and 34 ($X=5.33$).

Table 4: Mann Whitney U analysis results regarding the relation between job satisfaction levels of the participants and the variable of sex

	Sex	N	Mean Rank	Sum of mean rank	Z	P
Intrinsic Satisfaction	Female	1	17.00	17.00	-.572	.694
	Male	48	25.17	1208.00		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	Female	1	25.50	25.50	-.036	.980
	Male	48	24.99	1199.50		
General Satisfaction	Female	1	22.00	22.00	-.213	.898
	Male	48	25.06	1203.00		

According to the analysis results, it has been ascertained that no significant difference exists between the job satisfaction and the variable of sex ($p>0.05$).

Table 5: Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between job satisfaction levels of the participants and the variable of education

	Educational Background	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P
Intrinsic Satisfaction	Primary and Secondary School	0	0	11.989	.002*
	High School	0	0		
	Associate Degree	1	1.00		
	Bachelor's Degree	36	29.06		
	Master's Degree and PhD	12	14.83		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	Primary and Secondary School	0	0	17.626	.000*
	High School	0	0		
	Associate Degree	1	4.00		
	Bachelor's Degree	36	30.06		
	Master's Degree and PhD	12	11.58		
General Satisfaction	Primary and Secondary School	0	0	14.887	.001*
	High School	0	0		
	Associate Degree	1	1.00		

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	Bachelor's Degree	36	29.61		
	Master's Degree and PhD	12	13.17		

According to the analysis results, it has been determined that there is a significant difference between the sub-dimensions of extrinsic and intrinsic satisfaction scores of the participants and general satisfaction scores and the variable of educational background. Mann Whitney U statistics has been performed with the purpose of determining the source of emerging significance.

Accordingly, it has been established that the scores of the individuals with bachelor's degree ($X= 29.06$) are significantly higher than the scores of the individuals with master's degree and PhD ($X= 10.83$) in the extrinsic satisfaction sub-dimension. Similarly, it has been determined that the scores of the individuals with bachelor's degree ($X= 28.06$) are significantly higher than the scores of the individuals with master's degree and PhD ($X= 13.83$) in the intrinsic satisfaction sub-dimension. Lastly, it has been stated that the scores of the individuals with bachelor's degree ($X= 28.61$) are significantly higher than the scores of the individuals with master's degree and PhD ($X= 12.17$) in the general satisfaction sub-dimension.

Table 6: Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between job satisfaction levels of the participants and the variable of term of employment

	Term of Employment	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P
Intrinsic Satisfaction	1-5	3	18.17	3.608	.307
	6-10	0	0		
	11-15	4	33.00		
	16-20	13	28.88		
	21 and above	29	22.86		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	1-5	3	7.17	5.900	.117
	6-10	0	0		
	11-15	4	32.25		
	16-20	13	25.54		
	21 and above	29	25.60		
General Satisfaction	1-5	3	9.50	5.508	.138
	6-10	0	0		
	11-15	4	33.50		
	16-20	13	27.65		
	21 and above	29	24.24		

According to the analysis results, no significant difference has been established between the job satisfaction and term of employment ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Kruskal Wallis analysis results regarding the relation between job satisfaction levels of the participants and the variable of term of employment as manager

	Term of employment as manager	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	P
Intrinsic Satisfaction	1-5	37	24.62	4.628	.328
	6-10	4	33.63		
	11-15	3	16.50		
	16-20	1	44.00		
	21 and above	4	21.50		
Extrinsic Satisfaction	1-5	37	23.85	3.580	.466
	6-10	4	32.50		
	11-15	3	27.83		
	16-20	1	44.00		
	21 and above	4	21.25		
General Satisfaction	1-5	37	24.47	4.220	.377
	6-10	4	33.25		
	11-15	3	21.83		
	16-20	1	45.00		
	21 and above	4	19.00		

According to the analysis results, no significant difference has been established between the job satisfaction and term of employment as manager ($p>0.05$).

Table 8: Correlation analysis

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Self-esteem	1.000	-.115	-.237*	.248*	.082	.134	.131	-.199	-	-.077	-.245	-
Intrinsic satisfaction		1.000	.724(**)	.930(**)	.090	.116	.335(*)	.230	.044	.105	.291(*)	.137
Extrinsic satisfaction			1.000	.893(**)	.245	.367(**)	.057	.284(*)	-.030	-.160	.317(*)	-.054
General satisfaction				1.000	.178	.221	.221	.259	-.027	-.012	.337(*)	.090

** $p<0.01$

* $p<0.05$

Considering the results of Spearman correlation analysis, it has been determined that there is a negatively moderate relation between the self-esteem and extrinsic satisfaction ($r=-0.237$, $p<0.05$). Also, it has been ascertained that there is a positively moderate relation between the self-esteem and general satisfaction ($r=0.248$, $p<0.05$).

4. Discussion

It has been determined in our study that there is a negatively moderate relation between self-esteem and extrinsic satisfaction and positively moderate relation between self-esteem and general satisfaction. In a study of Balkar (2009) conducted on pre-school teachers, a highly positive and significant relation has been found between the self-esteem of teachers and job satisfaction and it is stated that the higher self-esteem of teachers are, the higher job satisfaction becomes. In a study of Erbil and Bostan (2004), the relation between the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction and self-esteem has been analyzed and a positively advanced and very weak relation has been found between intrinsic satisfaction, general satisfaction and self-esteem. In the study of Aydoğın (2011) conducted on basketball players, it has been concluded that the athletes with high self-esteem have higher and fulfilling job satisfaction. In the study of Aydoğın (2012) performed on football players, it has been ascertained that there is a positive relation between the self-esteem scores and general job satisfaction, intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction scores. In the study of Aslan (2006) on working individuals, whether the self-esteem level changes depending on the job satisfaction levels has been analyzed and a positive relation has been established between the job satisfaction and self-esteem variables. While these studies are in parallel to the results of our study, Balođlu et al. (2006) has concluded in their research analyzing the relation between the professional self-esteem of primary school teachers and their job satisfaction that the higher the professional self-esteem levels of teachers are, the lower their job satisfaction level – composed of intrinsic and extrinsic dimensions – become.

In our study, no significant difference has been observed between the self-esteem and the variables of age, sex, marital status, educational background, term of employment and term of employment as manager. In the study of Balkar (2009) conducted on pre-school teachers, no significant relation has been found between the variable of age and self-esteem. However, Aydoğın (2012) has stated in the study performed on Professional football players that self-esteem scores significantly differ among the groups by the variable of age and the self-esteem scores of the participants aged between 15 and 19 are significantly higher than the participants aged 30 and above. Balkar (2009) has found that the scores of pre-school teachers with 1-5 years of seniority are significantly higher than the scores of those having 21 years of seniority and more with regard to the variable of seniority year. Erbil and Bostan (2004) couldn't find a significant difference between the type of employment, term of employment and self-esteem.

In our study, it has been pointed out that there is no significant difference between the job satisfaction and the variables of sex, term of employment and term of employment as manager. Similarly, while no statistically significant relation has been determined between job satisfaction and sex as in the studies of Yağız and Yaman (2003), Tilev and Beydağ (2014), Aslan (2006) has stated in the study that job satisfaction levels of males are higher than females and proved that sex is a significant difference. In the study of Usta (2015) conducted on job satisfaction of form teachers, it is indicated that there is no significant difference between the seniority and job satisfaction averages. In the study of Aslan (2006), it has been determined that term of employment doesn't have a significant effect on job satisfaction.

Unlike the results of our study, Şahin et al. (2012) has stated that extrinsic job satisfaction levels differ by the term of employment, the auditors with 15 years and below seniority get considerably higher satisfaction than all auditors in other groups and the auditors having 21 years and more seniority get considerably higher satisfaction than the auditors with 16-20 years of seniority. However, intrinsic job satisfaction levels of education auditors don't differ significantly by the term of employment in the same study. In the research of Öztekin (2008), the employees working for 10 years and more are more inclined to state high job satisfaction with regard to the term of employment. Similarly, the employees working for 3-7 years in an organization utter less job satisfaction than the other groups with different terms of employment in the organization. Baykoca (2012) has determined that job satisfaction is at the highest level for the 0-5 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and more.

It has been determined in our study that the scores of individuals with bachelor's degree in the sub-dimensions of extrinsic, intrinsic and general satisfaction are significantly higher than the scores of the individuals with master's degree and PhD. In the study of Baykoca (2012), it is observed that there is a significant difference between the job satisfaction of employees and their educational background, the employees with the highest level of job satisfaction are high school graduates and the lowest ranking administrative personnel has a master's degree. This result complies with our study and indicates that the individuals with low educational level have higher job satisfaction than those with high educational level.

In the study of Akpınar and Kuru (2011) unlike our study, a statistically significant difference has been found in terms of intrinsic satisfaction being among the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction scale and those with a master's degree have higher job satisfaction than those with high school, associate and bachelor's degree. While Tilev and Beydağ (2014) don't find a statistically significant relation between the job satisfaction levels of nurses and their educational status, Aydoğan (2012) has stated that

there is no significant difference between the general, extrinsic and intrinsic satisfaction of professional football players being the sub-dimensions of the job satisfaction scale and the variable of education.

It has been ascertained in our study that there is a significant difference between the scores of extrinsic satisfaction being among the sub-dimensions of job satisfaction and the variable of age, the extrinsic satisfaction scores of the individuals aged 40 and above are significantly higher than the individuals aged between 30-34. In the study of Baykoca (2012) and Esen (2001), it is observed that job satisfaction levels significantly differ by the age and the older the personnel get, the more job satisfaction becomes. It has been delivered in the study of Aydođan (2012) that the job satisfaction scores of the participants aged 30 and above are significantly higher than the participants aged between 20-24 with regard to the intrinsic job satisfaction.

Unlike these studies not complying with our study, Aydođan (2012) has stated that the job satisfaction scores of the individuals aged between 15-19 are significantly higher than those aged 30 and above in terms of the general job satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction of Professional football players. Tekirgöl (2011) has found the significant difference between the job satisfaction score and the variable of age. Accordingly, general satisfaction, intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic satisfaction scores of the individuals in the age group of 20-25 are higher than the other age groups. In contrast to the findings obtained, Aslan (2006) couldn't find a significant difference between job satisfaction and the variable of age. In two separate studies conducted by Yürür (2008) and Aydođan (2011), it has been concluded that there is no significant difference between the variable of age ranking among the demographic characteristics and the job satisfaction.

In this age witnessing continuous changes and developments, management processes become more complicated and the organizations are continuously growing and getting more complicated. New developments in technology augment the need for new knowledge and skills both on organizational and the individual basis and they also cause new needs and expectations to emerge (Şahin, 2010;21). At this stage, the provincial directors being the representatives of the Ministry of Youth and Sports – fulfilling important functions in shaping particularly future generations – in the provinces must be engaged in the activities that will increase their motivations, organizational commitments and job satisfactions in order to guide “human resource” - being accepted as the most effective resource for the organizations to sustain – in line with the organizational purposes (Şahin, 2013;20).

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